

REDEFINING LEADERSHIP: GENDER EQUITY IN NIGERIAN CORPORATE BOARDS AND EXECUTIVE ROLES

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Abstract

This paper critically explores the evolving landscape of gender equity within Nigerian corporate leadership, focusing on the representation of women on corporate boards and in executive roles. As the global push for inclusive leadership gains momentum, the corporate sector in Nigeria is increasingly scrutinised for its progress in achieving gender-balanced governance. This research delves into these complexities by investigating the persistent barriers and the emerging opportunities that shape gender representation in Nigerian corporate governance today. Employing a qualitative methodology, the study draws on in-depth interviews conducted with female executives and board members across various industries in Nigeria. These interviews offer valuable insights into how entrenched cultural norms, pervasive gender biases, and restricted access to decision-making networks pose significant challenges for women aspiring to leadership positions. Furthermore, the study examines the scarcity of female role models in senior roles, which further complicates mentorship opportunities and career progression for women. In addition to these barriers, the research critically evaluates existing corporate policies and diversity initiatives, assessing their effectiveness in promoting gender equity and identifying areas where further progress is needed. The findings reveal that although there has been some progress in increasing the visibility of women in leadership roles within Nigerian corporations, substantial gaps remain. The study identifies several promising avenues for improvement, including the implementation of robust gender quotas, the development of comprehensive mentorship programs, and the adoption of policies that support work-life balance, which are crucial strategies for retaining and advancing women in leadership. This paper contributes to the ongoing discourse on gender equity in corporate leadership by offering a focused analysis of the Nigerian context. It provides actionable recommendations for corporate leaders and policymakers committed to advancing gender equity in Nigerian boardrooms and executive suites. The insights from this study are intended to guide immediate and long-term strategies for empowering women in leadership, ultimately contributing to more sustainable business practices and broader societal progress.

Keywords: Corporate governance, Cultural barriers, Executive roles, Gender equity, Nigerian corporate boards, Leadership diversity

1. INTRODUCTION

Gender equity in corporate leadership has become a global concern, with various regions showing varying levels of progress. Worldwide, efforts to achieve balanced gender representation on corporate boards have gained momentum, supported by numerous studies emphasizing the benefits of inclusivity in leadership roles. For instance, research suggests that gender diversity on boards leads to improved decision-making, innovation, and financial performance (Erin et al., 2021). However, despite these positive trends, many countries, especially in emerging economies, lag behind in ensuring equal representation of men and women in corporate governance. Countries such as Nigeria face unique socio-cultural and institutional challenges that hinder the progression of women into leadership roles. These challenges include gender biases, traditional norms, and the balancing of work and family responsibilities, which often reinforce male dominance in leadership positions (Adeyemi & Fajana, 2016; Okafor & Akokuwebe, 2015). Globally, there is a growing recognition that corporate leadership should reflect societal diversity, with an emphasis on fostering an environment that supports both male and female leaders equally, ultimately driving better governance and corporate outcomes (Ayeni-Agbaje, 2024).

The importance of gender-balanced governance in the corporate sector is paramount, as diverse leadership teams are known to provide a broader range of perspectives, contributing to enhanced problem-solving and innovation. Gender-inclusive boards ensure fairness and contribute to more effective corporate strategies and sustainable business practices (Otegunrin, 2024; Olutimehin, 2024). Studies have shown that companies with gender-balanced boards often perform better in financial performance (Asikhia, 2023), employee retention (Eleng et al., 2022), and sustainability reporting. Moreover, gender diversity in governance is crucial in promoting transparency, accountability, and stakeholder engagement (Oriakhi, 2020). Therefore, achieving gender-balanced governance is not just a matter of fairness but a strategic imperative that can drive better corporate results and contribute to broader societal and economic development.

2. CURRENT STATE OF GENDER REPRESENTATION ON NIGERIAN CORPORATE BOARDS AND IN EXECUTIVE ROLES

The current state of gender representation on Nigerian corporate boards and executive roles continues to highlight significant disparities despite ongoing global and national efforts to improve inclusivity. In Nigerian corporate governance, women remain underrepresented in leadership positions, with most corporate boards dominated by men (Adeyemi & Fajana, 2016; Okafor & Akokuwebe, 2015). This gender imbalance is particularly evident in key sectors such as oil, gas, and finance, where cultural norms and institutional barriers have historically hindered the advancement of women into top leadership roles (Asikhia, 2023). While some progress has been made, the advancement remains slow, and many Nigerian firms have yet to adopt the transformative policies necessary to achieve gender parity (Erin et al., 2021; Oriakhi, 2020). However, introducing corporate governance reforms and recognising gender diversity as a driver of enhanced performance has created a growing awareness of the need to promote women into decision-making roles.

The relevance of this study within the Nigerian corporate landscape is critical as it addresses the multifaceted challenges that continue to impede the progress toward gender inclusivity in leadership. Nigeria's corporate sector has been shifting its governance structures, with regulatory bodies increasingly focusing on creating frameworks prioritising gender diversity and equitable representation (Otegunrin, 2024; Eleng et al., 2022). This study contributes to ongoing discussions by exploring the cultural, social, and institutional factors that influence gender roles and representation in Nigerian corporate governance, offering actionable insights for policymakers and corporate leaders. By focusing on the Nigerian context, where traditional gender norms often intersect with modern corporate practices, this research provides a nuanced understanding of how gender inclusivity can be fostered to drive organisational effectiveness, sustainability, and inclusive economic growth (Olutimehin, 2024; Ayeni-Agbaje, 2024).

3. RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

1. Investigate barriers and opportunities for gender equity in Nigerian corporate leadership
2. Offer actionable recommendations for advancing women in leadership roles.

4. GLOBAL PERSPECTIVE ON GENDER EQUITY IN CORPORATE LEADERSHIP

Achieving gender equity in corporate leadership remains an ongoing global challenge, marked by progress and persistent barriers. Key trends indicate that while there is growing recognition of the benefits of gender-diverse boards, many regions still struggle to implement effective policies that promote inclusivity. Studies by Sunita (2022) and Sarhan et al. (2018) emphasise that gender diversity on corporate boards is a moral and ethical issue and a strategic asset. Sunita (2022) highlights that gender-diverse boards lead to improved decision-making processes, critical for navigating complex business environments and ensuring organisational resilience. Sarhan et al. (2018) further established a positive correlation between female representation and improved corporate performance, showing that gender diversity in governance aligns executive compensation with long-term organisational goals and enhances overall effectiveness.

However, significant challenges remain in achieving gender equity worldwide. These challenges are particularly pronounced in regions where cultural, religious, and institutional norms heavily influence corporate governance structures. For example, Gupta et al. (2022) provide insights into how these factors can either facilitate or impede the implementation of gender diversity policies. In many parts of Asia and Africa, traditional gender norms limit women's participation in leadership roles, even as global research highlights the business advantages of diverse leadership teams (Roy, 2022). Bakar et al. (2019) found that gender diversity positively affects sustainability reporting in Malaysia. Still, similar progress has been slower in other emerging markets, such as Nigeria, where cultural and institutional barriers persist (Ebimobowei, 2022). This suggests that while the benefits of gender diversity are universal, the pathways to achieving equity must be tailored to different regions' socio-economic and cultural contexts.

The role of inclusive leadership in sustainable business practices is increasingly recognised as critical. Research shows that gender-diverse boards are more likely to engage in comprehensive and transparent corporate social responsibility (CSR) and environmental sustainability practices. Khan et al. (2019) found that gender-diverse boards are more proactive in CSR disclosures, contributing to higher corporate ethical standards and building public trust. Similarly, Kılınçarslan et al. (2020) demonstrated that gender diversity positively influences environmental disclosures, underscoring the importance of diverse leadership in advancing sustainable business practices. The intersection of gender diversity and sustainability is particularly relevant in industries with stringent environmental expectations, where inclusive leadership fosters innovation and more balanced decision-making.

Additionally, inclusive leadership teams are better positioned to navigate the tensions between profitability and sustainability, particularly in hybrid organisations, where balancing financial goals with social responsibility is critical. Reynolds & Holt (2021) highlight how diverse leadership teams, particularly those with strong female representation, are more adept at integrating these dual objectives. Their findings suggest that gender-diverse boards are essential for long-term sustainability, as they bring varied perspectives that enhance strategic and ethical decision-making. In this way, gender diversity supports more responsible business practices and contributes to a firm's resilience in adapting to global sustainability challenges.

5. GENDER EQUITY IN NIGERIA'S CORPORATE SECTOR

Nigeria's corporate sector has historically been marked by significant gender disparities in leadership and corporate governance. Women's participation in corporate governance has been limited due to deep-rooted socio-cultural norms that prioritize male leadership. Historically, Nigerian women have faced significant barriers, including traditional expectations regarding gender roles, which have largely confined women to domestic and supportive roles within the economy. As noted by Okunade (2023), these socio-cultural norms have contributed to the marginalization of women in both economic and corporate contexts, creating structural barriers that inhibit their progression into leadership roles. Despite these challenges, there has been a gradual shift over the past decade as gender diversity on corporate boards has increasingly become a priority. However, the pace of progress remains slow, with Nigerian boards still predominantly male-dominated, particularly in key industries such as oil and gas, where entrenched patriarchal structures continue to limit women's leadership opportunities (Adeyemi & Fajana, 2016; Asikhia, 2023).

In a comparative analysis with other African nations, Nigeria's progress toward gender equity in corporate governance lags behind countries such as South Africa and Rwanda, which have made significant strides in promoting gender diversity. For example, South Africa has implemented comprehensive policies, including gender quotas, to ensure women's representation on corporate boards. This has resulted in a more balanced corporate leadership landscape compared to Nigeria, where the implementation of similar policies has been

slower and less effective. Rwanda stands out as a global leader in gender parity, particularly in government and corporate governance, with women occupying a large percentage of leadership roles across various sectors. Nigeria, in contrast, continues to face challenges related to entrenched socio-cultural norms and institutional barriers that impede the full inclusion of women in corporate leadership positions (Makama, 2013).

Compared to global benchmarks, Nigeria remains behind in achieving gender equity in corporate governance. In many developed countries, especially in Europe, gender quotas and inclusive policies have significantly increased female representation on corporate boards. Countries like Norway have implemented mandatory quotas, resulting in female representation exceeding 40% on corporate boards, whereas in Nigeria, gender diversity remains much lower. Furthermore, international studies highlight that gender-diverse boards contribute to improved corporate governance, decision-making, and financial performance (Sunita, 2022; Sarhan et al., 2018), yet Nigerian companies are still in the early stages of recognizing these benefits. Ebimobowei (2022) notes that, while gender diversity positively impacts firm value in Nigeria, the socio-cultural barriers and lack of regulatory enforcement mean that these benefits are not being fully realized.

6. BARRIERS TO GENDER EQUITY IN LEADERSHIP

Cultural norms and gender biases are deeply embedded in Nigerian corporate environments, significantly impeding the progress of women into leadership roles. In Nigeria, socio-cultural barriers rooted in traditional gender roles have long perpetuated the belief that men are more suited for leadership positions, reinforcing male dominance in the corporate sphere. As Makama (2013) noted, these cultural norms prioritise male leadership and continue to marginalise women in decision-making processes. These barriers are particularly pronounced in male-dominated industries, where women's contributions are undervalued, and their leadership potential is often overlooked (Nwoye, 2011). The persistence of these socio-cultural norms creates systemic gender biases, making it difficult for women to break through the "glass ceiling" and advance into leadership positions in corporate governance. Okunade (2023) also emphasizes that these cultural barriers, rooted in traditional expectations, act as significant obstacles to women's empowerment and participation in the corporate sector.

Structural challenges within Nigerian corporate governance further exacerbate the barriers to gender equity in leadership. One major challenge is the lack of access to decision-making networks, which are often dominated by men. These networks, formed through informal relationships and social circles, tend to exclude women, limiting their opportunities for advancement. As noted by Ujunwa et al. (2012), board composition in Nigeria, including factors like gender and ethnicity, has a significant impact on firm performance, yet the entrenched power dynamics within these networks often prevent women from accessing these leadership opportunities. The scarcity of mentorship programs also plays a critical role in hindering women's progression into leadership roles. Adegbite (2012) critiques the weak regulatory environment and lack of corporate transparency in Nigeria, which often results in a lack of accountability in ensuring diversity and inclusion. Without effective mentorship and sponsorship programs, women in Nigeria face additional challenges in navigating their career paths and gaining the necessary support to move into executive positions.

These structural challenges are compounded by a lack of formal policies promoting gender inclusivity in corporate governance, particularly in the private sector. While public sector reforms have made some progress, the private sector remains slow to adopt policies that address these gender disparities. Adegboye et al. (2020) highlight that ineffective governance frameworks and weak enforcement mechanisms contribute to the persistence of these barriers, making it difficult to create an inclusive environment where women can thrive in leadership roles.

7. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

7.1. Research Design

The research design for this study employs a qualitative methodology, which is well-suited for exploring complex social phenomena, such as gender inclusivity in Nigerian corporate governance. Unlike quantitative methods that focus on numerical data, qualitative research enables an in-depth examination of personal experiences, perceptions, and societal dynamics (Creswell, 2013). This approach is particularly appropriate for investigating the intricate power dynamics, cultural norms, and organizational structures that shape gender inclusivity in leadership roles (Egbunike et al., 2023). Through methods like interviews and document

analysis, qualitative research allows for the exploration of the nuanced experiences of women in corporate governance, providing richer insights that quantitative measures may overlook (Shabi et al., 2014).

7.2. Data Collection

Data collection for this study primarily involved in-depth, semi-structured interviews with female executives and board members from various industries in Nigeria, including sectors like banking, telecommunications, education, and agriculture. These interviews were chosen to capture the diverse perspectives and lived experiences of women in leadership positions (Monteiro, 2024). Semi-structured interviews provided flexibility, allowing participants to discuss their experiences with gender dynamics in corporate governance while enabling the researcher to explore emergent themes in detail (Kvale & Brinkmann, 2015). The sampling techniques used included purposive sampling, which ensured that participants had a minimum of five years of leadership experience, allowing them to provide meaningful insights into the barriers and opportunities they encountered (Adegbite, 2012). Additionally, snowball sampling was employed to expand the participant pool, with initial participants referring to other female leaders who met the criteria, thus broadening the scope of the study (Goodman, 2011).

7.3. Data Analysis

The data collected through interviews were analyzed using thematic analysis, a method effective for identifying, analyzing, and reporting patterns (themes) within qualitative data. This analysis focused on uncovering key trends, barriers, and opportunities related to gender equity in Nigerian corporate governance. The thematic analysis allowed the researcher to interpret the data in a structured way, providing insights into how cultural norms, organizational practices, and individual experiences shape leadership opportunities for women (Damoah et al., 2021). By identifying recurring themes, the study highlighted both the systemic barriers women face in leadership roles and the strategies that have been successful in promoting gender inclusivity (Kroese, 2022).

8. LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

One significant limitation of this study was the challenge of gathering comprehensive data from male executives and policymakers, who often hold key decision-making roles in corporate governance structures. Their perspectives could have provided a more holistic understanding of the gender dynamics at play, but they were underrepresented in the data due to difficulties in recruitment (Monteiro, 2024). Another limitation was time and participant availability constraints, which affected the breadth of data collection. High-level executives often have limited time, making it challenging to schedule interviews and obtain in-depth responses from a larger pool of participants. Despite these constraints, the study still provides valuable insights into the experiences of female leaders in Nigerian corporate governance and highlights areas for further research (Ayoola, 2023).

9. FINDINGS

9.1. Persistent Barriers to Gender Equity in Leadership

Cultural norms and deeply entrenched gender biases continue to pose significant obstacles to women's career advancement in Nigeria. Respondent 12 notes, "*Cultural expectations about gender roles are still very strong, and they often hinder women's progress in the corporate world.*" These societal expectations not only limit women's professional opportunities but also reinforce traditional gender roles, such as prioritising family responsibilities over career aspirations. Additionally, women face challenges in accessing decision-making networks, which are often male-dominated; as Respondent 11 highlights, "*Men often dominate discussions, especially if they are in leadership roles. This can marginalise women's voices.*" This limited access to executive circles hinders women's ability to influence high-level decisions and reduces their opportunities for career advancement.

9.2. Challenges Related to Mentorship and Role Models

A significant challenge for aspiring female is the lack of senior female role models in Nigerian corporate leadership. Respondent 17 points out, "*Finding a mentor who really understands the specific challenges women face is still a major issue.*" Without visible female leaders to guide and inspire, many women find it difficult to navigate their career paths. Respondent 16 adds that mentorship programs, though present in some organizations, are often superficial and fail to address the unique needs of women in leadership roles: "*Mentorship programs are in place, but they often feel like a formality rather than a real effort to uplift women*

leaders.” This lack of meaningful mentorship opportunities limits women’s ability to grow and develop the skills necessary for executive roles.

9.3. Corporate Policies and Diversity Initiatives

While some Nigerian corporations have implemented gender diversity programs, their effectiveness is often questioned. Respondent 5 emphasizes the gap between policy and practice: *“There are so many policies that favour women in Nigeria, but women don’t know about them, and we don’t take advantage of those things.”* This lack of awareness and inadequate enforcement of existing policies undermines their potential to create real change. Additionally, structural challenges like tokenism persist, where diversity initiatives are more symbolic than substantive. Respondent 16 observes, *“Mentorship opportunities exist, but they are not always accessible or tailored to women’s unique challenges.”* These limitations highlight the need for a more robust commitment to gender equity, with policies that are not just designed but actively applied and supported.

10. DISCUSSION

10.1. Progress in Gender Representation on Corporate Boards

There has been some progress in increasing women’s representation on corporate boards in Nigeria. Respondent 12 notes, *“Compared to ten years ago, there are definitely more women in leadership positions now, which is encouraging.”* However, despite these gains, the pace of change remains slow, with cultural and societal expectations continuing to restrict women’s advancement. In certain industries, particularly in regions with conservative gender norms, progress has been even slower. Respondent 10 mentions, *“The difficulty in achieving the 35% women inclusion target in northern states due to cultural restrictions illustrates a systemic challenge.”* This suggests that while visibility for women has improved, regional and industry-specific barriers remain.

10.2. Emerging Opportunities for Enhancing Gender Equity

Gender quotas and affirmative action have been suggested as potential solutions for achieving balanced gender representation. Respondent 11 advocates for quotas: *“Setting a minimum percentage of women in certain positions and ensuring compliance through legislation can drive change.”* Additionally, mentorship programs and networking opportunities are essential for supporting women’s career advancement. Respondent 12 highlights the importance of networks: *“Joining a women’s leadership network has been incredibly beneficial. The mentorship and support I receive have helped me navigate my career more effectively.”* These initiatives can provide the guidance and support women need to reach leadership positions and combat systemic gender bias.

10.3. Work-Life Balance Policies

Family-friendly policies, such as flexible work hours and maternity leave, are critical for retaining women in senior leadership roles. Respondent 13 underscores the importance of these policies: *“Flexible work arrangements would make it much easier for women to juggle their careers and family responsibilities.”* However, current corporate support for work-life integration in Nigeria is often inadequate. Respondent 9 notes the need for more comprehensive policies: *“Supportive policies, such as reintegration plans for women returning from maternity leave, help create a more inclusive work environment.”* Without such policies, many women struggle to balance their professional and personal responsibilities, which can limit their career advancement.

11. RECOMMENDATIONS

11.1. Implementing Gender Quotas

To address the gender imbalance in Nigerian corporate leadership, a framework for establishing and enforcing gender quotas on corporate boards and executive roles is essential. These quotas would mandate a minimum percentage of leadership positions held by women, helping to dismantle the systemic barriers that prevent women from advancing in male-dominated sectors. Respondent 11 supports this: *“Setting a minimum percentage of women in certain positions and ensuring compliance through legislation can drive change.”* Regulatory bodies should enforce these quotas through penalties for non-compliance while offering financial incentives or public recognition for companies that exceed gender diversity targets. Regular reviews and audits should ensure transparency and accountability in the implementation process.

11.2. Mentorship and Sponsorship Programs

Developing structured mentorship and sponsorship programs is critical for nurturing future female leaders in Nigeria's corporate sector. Respondent 12 highlights the importance of mentorship, stating, "*Joining a women's leadership network has been incredibly beneficial. The mentorship and support I receive have helped me navigate my career more effectively.*" These programs should pair aspiring female leaders with experienced executives who can provide guidance, career development advice, and access to important decision-making networks. Sponsorship, where senior leaders actively advocate for the advancement of high-potential women, is equally important in fast-tracking women into leadership roles. Mentorship programs should be tailored to address the specific challenges that women face, offering practical strategies for overcoming gender biases and navigating male-dominated environments.

11.3. Corporate Policy Reforms

Comprehensive corporate policy reforms are necessary to support work-life balance, particularly for women in leadership roles. Flexible work arrangements, including remote work, part-time positions, and extended maternity/paternity leave, are essential for allowing women to manage both their professional and family responsibilities. Respondent 13 underscores the importance of such policies: "*Flexible work arrangements would make it much easier for women to juggle their careers and family responsibilities.*" Corporations should also implement reintegration programs for women returning from maternity leave, ensuring that they are not disadvantaged when resuming leadership roles. Additionally, companies should be incentivized to promote gender diversity initiatives, with government policies offering tax breaks, public recognition, or other rewards for organizations that implement and sustain effective diversity programs.

12. CONCLUSION

This study identified persistent barriers to gender equity in Nigerian corporate leadership, including entrenched cultural norms, gender biases, and limited access to decision-making networks. As Respondent 12 noted, "*Cultural expectations about gender roles are still very strong, and they often hinder women's progress in the corporate world.*" However, the study also uncovered opportunities for enhancing gender diversity, such as the introduction of gender quotas, structured mentorship programs, and work-life balance policies that can facilitate women's career advancement.

12.1. Contributions to Gender Equity Discourse

This study contributes to the ongoing discourse on gender equity in Nigerian corporate leadership by offering actionable insights into both the systemic barriers women face and the potential solutions for overcoming these obstacles. It reinforces the idea that achieving gender equity requires policy reforms and quotas and a cultural shift within corporate governance structures. The findings add depth to the conversation around gender inclusivity, particularly within the Nigerian context, where traditional gender roles continue to intersect with modern corporate practices.

12.2. Future Research

Future research should explore the long-term impacts of gender quotas on corporate performance in Nigeria and the effectiveness of mentorship and sponsorship programs across different industries. Additional studies could focus on the regional variations in gender equity, examining how cultural differences across Nigeria influence the success of gender diversity initiatives. Lastly, a closer examination of how corporate policies, such as flexible work arrangements, affect women's retention and advancement in leadership roles would provide valuable insights into improving gender equity in governance.

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